

Figure S1. Flowchart of participant recruitment.

Table S1. Characteristics of newborns in the three treatment conditions at birth and at time of heel stick.

Characteristic	Treatment Condition			p
	Condition 1 (n = 40)	Condition 2 (n = 40)	Condition 3 (n = 40)	
Gestational age, weeks (M ± SD)	39.42 ± 1.00	39.07 ± 1.09	38.91±0.97	0.078 ^a
Birth weight, g (M ± SD)	3121 ± 347.15	3109.38 ± 375.91	3070.38 ± 340.76	0.828 ^a
Gender (n, %)				0.565 ^b
Male	17 (42.5%)	22 (55.0%)	20 (50.0%)	
Female	23 (57.5%)	18 (45.0%)	20 (50.0%)	
Delivery type, n (%)				0.137 ^b
Normal spontaneous delivery	32 (80)	24 (60)	26 (65)	
Caesarean delivery	8 (20)	16 (40)	14 (35)	
Parity, n (%)				0.638 ^b
1	25 (62.5)	20 (50.0)	21 (52.5)	
2	10 (25.0)	16 (40.0)	13 (32.5)	
3	4 (10.0)	4 (10.0)	6 (15.0)	
4	1 (2.5)	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)	
Age in days	3.00± 0.00	3.00± 0.00	3.00± 0.00	> 0.999 ^a
Apgar score, M ± SD				
1 min	7.88 ± 0.33	7.88 ± 0.33	7.88 ± 0.33	> 0.999 ^a
5 min	9.00 ± 0.00	8.98 ± 0.15	8.98 ± 0.15	0.604 ^a
At time of heel stick (baseline)				
Time since feeding, min (M ± SD)	80.00 ± 50.33	64.75 ± 47.98	80.12 ± 44.18	0.098 ^a
Prior painful experiences (n, %)	2.53 ± 0.55	2.40 ± 0.50	2.38 ± 0.49	0.437 ^b
NIPS score (M ± SD)	0.61 ± 0.95	0.46 ± 0.79	0.42 ± 0.82	0.749 ^a

Notes: M: mean; SD: standard deviation; NIPS: Neonatal Infant Pain Scale; Condition1: gentle touch+ verbal comfort (routine care); Condition2: breast milk odor + gentle touch+ verbal comfort; Condition3: breast milk odor+ taste + gentle touch+ verbal comfort; Phase1: baseline (no stimulation)

^aKruskal Wallis Test

^bFisher's Exact Test

Table S2. Changes in pain scores for breastmilk-odor (Condition 2), and breastmilk-odor+ breastmilk-taste (Condition 3) by GEE multiple linear regression with Condition 1 as reference (N = 120)

Variable	B	SE	Wald χ^2	P	95% CI	
					Lower	Upper
Condition effects						
Condition ₃ vs. Condition ₁	-0.152	0.116	1.717	0.190	-0.379	0.075
Condition ₂ vs. Condition ₁	-0.231	0.118	3.772	0.052	-0.464	0.002
Phase effects						
Phase ₁₁ vs. Phase ₁	1.247	0.361	11.937	0.001	0.540	1.955
Phase ₁₀ vs. Phase ₁	1.647	0.358	21.135	<0.001	0.945	2.350
Phase ₉ vs. Phase ₁	1.997	0.352	32.072	<0.001	1.306	2.689
Phase ₈ vs. Phase ₁	2.697	0.391	47.561	<0.001	1.931	3.464
Phase ₇ vs. Phase ₁	3.322	0.411	65.067	<0.001	2.515	4.130
Phase ₆ vs. Phase ₁	5.998	0.237	636.287	<0.001	5.531	6.464
Phase ₅ vs. Phase ₁	6.172	0.209	867.632	<0.001	5.762	6.583
Phase ₄ vs. Phase ₁	6.248	0.203	946.216	<0.001	5.849	6.646
Phase ₃ vs. Phase ₁	6.272	0.206	919.262	<0.001	5.867	6.678
Phase ₂ vs. Phase ₁	6.047	0.224	728.171	<0.001	5.608	6.487
Interaction effects						
Condition 3						
Condition ₃ × Phase ₁₁	-1.512	0.382	15.600	<0.001	-2.262	-0.762
Condition ₃ × Phase ₁₀	-1.737	0.381	20.762	<0.001	-2.484	-0.990
Condition ₃ × Phase ₉	-2.187	0.368	35.204	<0.001	-2.909	-1.464
Condition ₃ × Phase ₈	-2.737	0.410	44.361	<0.001	-3.542	-1.931
Condition ₃ × Phase ₇	-3.287	0.424	59.853	<0.001	-4.119	-2.545
Condition ₃ × Phase ₆	-4.362	0.450	93.954	<0.001	-5.244	-3.480
Condition ₃ × Phase ₅	-4.212	0.433	94.376	<0.001	-5.061	-3.362
Condition ₃ × Phase ₄	-3.562	0.409	75.801	<0.001	-4.364	-2.760
Condition ₃ × Phase ₃	-3.512	0.393	79.741	<0.001	-4.282	-2.741
Condition ₃ × Phase ₂	-3.212	0.388	68.200	<0.001	-3.974	-2.449
Condition 2						
Condition ₂ × Phase ₁₁	-1.112	0.377	8.586	0.003	-1.852	-0.373
Condition ₂ × Phase ₁₀	-1.588	0.374	17.997	<0.001	-2.321	-0.854
Condition ₂ × Phase ₉	-1.963	0.387	25.685	<0.001	-2.271	-1.204
Condition ₂ × Phase ₈	-2.712	0.405	44.778	<0.001	-3.507	-1.918
Condition ₂ × Phase ₇	-2.462	0.480	26.320	<0.001	-3.403	-1.522
Condition ₂ × Phase ₆	-1.912	0.504	14.362	<0.001	-2.902	-0.923
Condition ₂ × Phase ₅	-1.463	0.463	9.948	0.002	-2.371	-0.554
Condition ₂ × Phase ₄	-1.213	0.448	7.304	0.007	-2.092	-0.333
Condition ₂ × Phase ₃	-1.162	0.428	7.377	0.007	-2.001	-0.324
Condition ₂ × Phase ₂	-1.187	0.386	9.452	0.002	-1.945	-0.430
Baseline pain score	0.540	0.097	30.656	<0.001	0.349	0.731

Notes: SE: standard error; CI: confidence interval; Condition₁: gentle touch+ verbal comfort (routine care); Condition₂: breast milk odor + gentle touch+ verbal comfort; Condition₃: breast milk odor+ taste + gentle touch+ verbal comfort; Phase₁: baseline (no stimulation); Phase₂: 1st minute during heel stick; Phase₃: 2nd minute during heel stick; Phase₄: 3rd minute during heel stick; Phase₅: 4th minute during heel stick; Phase₆: 5th minute during heel stick; Phase₇: 1st minute after heel stick; Phase₈: 2nd minute after heel stick; Phase₉: 3rd minute after heel stick; Phase₁₀: 4th minute after heel stick; Phase₁₁: 5th minute after heel stick.

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Table S3. Changes in pain scores for Condition 1 (routine care), and Condition 3 (breastmilk-odor+ breastmilk-taste) by GEE multiple linear regression with Condition 2 (breastmilk-odor) as reference (N = 120)

Variable	B	SE	Waldχ ²	P	95% CI	
					Lower	Upper
Condition effects						
Condition ₃ vs. Condition ₂	0.079	.0934	0.714	0.398	-0.104	0.262
Condition ₁ vs. Condition ₂	0.231	.1189	3.772	0.052	-0.002	0.464
Phase effects						
Phase ₁₁ vs. Phase ₁	0.135	0.110	1.504	0.220	-0.081	0.351
Phase ₁₀ vs. Phase ₁	0.060	0.107	0.310	0.578	-0.151	0.271
Phase ₉ vs. Phase ₁	0.035	0.159	0.048	0.827	-0.278	0.348
Phase ₈ vs. Phase ₁	-0.015	0.106	0.020	0.888	0.224	0.194
Phase ₇ vs. Phase ₁	0.860	0.246	12.183	<0.001	0.377	1.343
Phase ₆ vs. Phase ₁	4.085	0.445	84.218	<0.001	3.213	4.957
Phase ₅ vs. Phase ₁	4.710	0.413	129.658	<0.001	3.899	5.521
Phase ₄ vs. Phase ₁	5.035	0.400	158.401	<0.001	4.251	5.819
Phase ₃ vs. Phase ₁	5.110	0.374	185.987	<0.001	4.376	5.844
Phase ₂ vs. Phase ₁	4.860	0.314	238.678	<0.001	4.243	5.477
Interaction effects						
Condition 3						
Condition ₃ × Phase ₁₁	-0.399	0.167	5.685	0.017	-0.727	-0.071
Condition ₃ × Phase ₁₀	-0.149	0.167	0.791	0.374	-0.478	0.180
Condition ₃ × Phase ₉	-0.224	0.192	1.362	0.243	-0.601	0.152
Condition ₃ × Phase ₈	-0.024	0.163	0.022	0.883	-0.345	0.297
Condition ₃ × Phase ₇	-0.824	0.266	9.546	0.002	-1.347	-0.301
Condition ₃ × Phase ₆	-2.449	0.586	17.424	<0.001	-3.599	-1.299
Condition ₃ × Phase ₅	-2.749	0.561	23.961	<0.001	-3.850	-1.648
Condition ₃ × Phase ₄	-2.349	0.535	19.260	<0.001	-3.398	-1.300
Condition ₃ × Phase ₃	-2.349	0.502	21.858	<0.001	-3.334	-1.364
Condition ₃ × Phase ₂	-2.024	0.447	20.475	<0.001	-2.901	-1.147
Condition 1						
Condition ₁ × Phase ₁₁	1.112	0.377	8.686	0.003	0.373	1.852
Condition ₁ × Phase ₁₀	1.587	0.374	17.997	<0.001	0.854	2.321
Condition ₁ × Phase ₉	1.962	0.387	25.685	<0.001	1.204	2.721
Condition ₁ × Phase ₈	2.712	0.405	44.778	<0.001	1.918	3.507
Condition ₁ × Phase ₇	2.462	0.480	26.320	<0.001	1.522	3.403
Condition ₁ × Phase ₆	1.912	0.504	14.362	<0.001	0.923	2.902
Condition ₁ × Phase ₅	1.462	0.463	9.948	0.002	0.554	2.371
Condition ₁ × Phase ₄	1.212	0.448	7.304	0.007	0.333	2.092
Condition ₁ × Phase ₃	1.162	0.428	7.377	0.007	0.324	2.001
Condition ₁ × Phase ₂	1.187	0.386	9.452	0.002	0.430	1.945
Baseline pain score	0.540	0.097	30.656	<0.001	0.349	0.731

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